

Conceptualizing the Capstone Project Through Possible Research Topics, Approaches, and Methods in Music for Senior High School Students

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Abstract

This paper aimed to briefly discuss conceptualizing a capstone project through possible research topics, approaches, and methods in music for senior high school students. In conceptualizing possible research topics in music, this paper includes two (2) categories: curriculum-aligned research topics and academic and practical research topics. For curriculum-aligned research topics, these were taken from the three (3) specialized subjects under the Arts and Design Track of the present K-12 curriculum, including the following: Creative Industries II: Performing Arts, Apprenticeship and Exploration in the Performing Arts (Music), and Production in the Performing Arts. On the other hand, academic and practical research topics were lifted from the author's works. Exemplary research topics and literature reviews were conducted through Google Scholar, as this platform provides a simple way to broadly search for scholarly literature. Google Scholar is a freely accessible web search engine that indexes the full text or metadata of scholarly literature across an array of publishing formats and disciplines. This initiative was to prepare senior high school students for lifelong learning through planning, implementing, and presenting a culminating project reflecting their personal interests and the competencies they have acquired in secondary education.

Keywords: capstone project, exemplar, music, research, research topic

I. Basic Considerations in Conceptualizing Possible Research Topics in Music (Tabuena, 2022)

II. Curriculum-Aligned Research Topics in Music

A. Creative Industries II: Performing Arts

The course introduces the students to principles of theater, music and dance and examines the practical application of the performing arts skills in the local and global market (Department of Education, 2013a).

1. Sight Reading and Ear Training
2. Ensemble and Band Playing - Piano or Keyboard, Guitar, Banduria, Wind Instruments, Traditional Instruments
3. Choral Singing and Conducting

Exemplar Research Topics for Sight Reading and Ear Training

Mishra, J. (2014). Factors related to sight-reading accuracy: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Research in Music Education*, 61(4), 452-465.

*The purpose of this meta-analysis was to determine the extent of the overall relationship between previously tested variables and sight-reading. An exhaustive survey of the available research literature was conducted resulting in 92 research studies that reported correlations between sight-reading and another variable. Variables (n = 597) were grouped by construct (e.g., music aptitude, technical ability) and separate meta-analyses were conducted for each construct. Construct had a variable effect on sight-reading, with improvisational skills, ear-training ability, technical ability, and music knowledge correlating most closely with sight-reading, while attitude and personality were unrelated to sight-reading. Additionally, the study examined differences in effect size by type of publication (published study, unpublished thesis), the experience level of the sight-reader (elementary, secondary, college nonmusician, college musician), sight-reading mode (instrumental sight-reading, sight-singing), and type of sight-reading test. The few differences suggest future investigation of a developmental component to sight-reading is warranted. In general, music constructs that improve with practice correlated more strongly with sight-reading than did stable characteristics. **These results support sight-reading being considered a music skill that improves with the musicality of the performer rather than a simple visuo-motor decoding process.***

Anderson, D. P. (1995). *Integrating instructional ear-training techniques into a high school choral music performance class curriculum to improve students' sight-reading skills*. Nova Southeastern University.

This practicum was designed to integrate time-efficient methods for teaching sight reading during performance classes. A crucial discovery was that music aptitude comprises both cognitive and perceptual processes. Choral students received music training in the mechanics of note and rhythm reading. Learning occurred through the discovery of correct tempo, rote and emulation concepts, music imaging (audiation), and developing mental presets. Cognitive applications, verbalizing goals and expectations, and the importance of the director's daily dispositions were discussed as vital elements of instruction. After 8 months of training, the lower quartile students raised their average score from 4.5 points to an average score of 16.7 points out of 40 points on the Arizona State Sight-Reading Testing Instrument. The second quartile raised their average score from 7.3 to 18.6 points. The third quartile raised their average score from 11.3 to 25.8 points, while the highest quartile raised their average score from 22.7 points to an average score of 35.7 points.

Schüler, N. (2021). *Modern approaches to teaching sight singing and ear training. Facta Universitatis. Series: Visual Arts and Music, 083-092.*

*Sight singing and ear training are difficult subjects to teach. Over the past decade, however, many new technological tools were developed that support educational endeavors. **Several of those tools, SmartMusic, SingSnap, EarTrainer (MusicDictation.app), and YouTube, were used at the beginning college-level aural skills courses to enhance sight singing and ear training instruction, especially in the context of enhancing audiation skills.** This article summarizes their use within aural skills courses and present experimental and anecdotal evidence of increased sight singing and ear training skills. More specifically, experimental (test) data as well as anecdotal (essay) evidence showed that (1) students were **much higher motivated to complete exercises** compared to 'traditional' aural skills exercises, (2) in a shorter period of time, students **performed much better than** in 'traditional' exercises of at least the same difficulty, (3) the students' **audiation abilities increased much more as a result of the exercises**, compared to 'traditional' exercises, and (4) students **showed a greater increase in solfege proficiency, compared to 'traditional' exercises.** The teaching approaches we have discussed also led to a greater independence from in-person instruction.*

Exemplar Research Topics for Ensemble and Band Playing

Goodrich, A. (2007). Peer mentoring in a high school jazz ensemble. *Journal of Research in Music Education, 55*(2), 94-114.

*The use of peer mentoring in a successful high school jazz band was explored during one academic year of instruction using ethnographic techniques. Participants included primary informants (student jazz band members, director, assistant director, adult mentors) and secondary informants (guidance counselor, principal, parents, nonjazz band member students). Data analysis revealed that peer mentoring contributed to the success of a high school jazz band. Five themes emerged: (a) mentoring from the adult perspective, (b) peer mentoring for musicianship, (c) mentoring in rehearsals, (d) mentoring outside jazz band rehearsals, and (e) social mentoring. Suggestions for **teacher educators include supporting, developing, and implementing peer mentoring, which can aid directors in instruction and rehearsal efficiency.***

Ma, J. Y., & Hall, R. (2018). Learning a part together: Ensemble learning and infrastructure in a competitive high school marching band. *Instructional Science, 46*(4), 507-532.

*This article **reports on a learning community that requires acting together in order to perform and to learn, an organization of shared activity across people and through time that we call ensemble learning.** We present a descriptive analysis of ensemble learning in a high school marching band performance season, following how "The Show" was designed by instructors, translated into coordinate "dots" for band members, then learned and "cleaned" by the ensemble. We investigate aspects of representational and social infrastructure that supported ensemble learning in activity, and how they shifted in relation to emergent goals of learners over the course of the season. The dynamic, multi-party performances under the changing spatial and social conditions that were the object of the band's learning (marching competitions over the course of the season) leveraged diverse physical and social perspectives on learning and activity, and interactional and representational routines evolved over the course of the season. Additionally, the elective nature of the activity supported the emergence of practice-linked learning and teaching identities. We use the case study to extend similar accounts of ensemble learning and learning communities, and consider how our findings might inform design when restoring or building new ensemble learning environments.*

Exemplar Research Topics for Choral Singing and Conducting

Durrant, C. (2009). Communicating and accentuating the aesthetic and expressive dimension in choral conducting. *International journal of music education*, 27(4), 326-340.

*This article considers the issues that are involved in effective choral conducting from an aesthetic dimension. Drawing upon research, theories and practice, it provides some insight into the nature of communication and the significance of gesture on vocal outcome as well as qualities of leadership concomitant with such musical activity. The article also reports on a research study that investigated the professional development of students and teachers in the area of choral conducting, focusing on their attitudes, skill acquisition and the importance attached to reflection on practice. **The findings reveal that consideration of what counts as effective conducting gesture and communication skill can promote better conducting and, consequently, better, more expressive singing.** In addition, the positive impact of self- and peer reflection on progress (both face-to-face and within a virtual learning environment) was also acknowledged. Certain suggestions for promoting effective musical leadership in the area of choral conducting are provided, in order to ground theoretical perspectives in practice.*

Durrant, C. (2005). Shaping identity through choral activity: Singers' and conductors' perceptions. *Research Studies in Music Education*, 24(1), 88-98.

*This article reports on a research project carried out in 2002, with funding from the United Kingdom's Arts and Humanities Research Board, on choral activity and its relationship to singers' identity. Using a model of effective choral conducting (Durrant 1996; 2003) as a starting point, a connection is sought between perceptions of the conducting role and of singing in the shaping of singers' identity. The project focused on the choral music traditions of Finland and Sweden, where choirs are noted for their fine-quality singing, imaginative use of folk music and extensive involvement. A qualitative methodology was adopted; specifically a descriptive and interpretive case study, using interviews with conductors and singers, extensive observation of choral rehearsals and, on occasions, concerts. Issues arising from the research are reported, including: the role of choral repertoire and national folk song, singers' reasons for engaging in choral activity and the role of conductors. The research confirmed (i) that **the musical and interpersonal skills of the conductor are vital in the motivation of the singers**, (ii) that **singers identify themselves socially as well as musically with a group**, (iii) that **choral activity enhanced these singers' sense of national and cultural identity through use of folk traditions and a creative approach to musical practice.***

B. Apprenticeship and Exploration in the Performing Arts (Music)

This subject offers exploratory study of local music genres and information and communication technologies (ICT) applications in music while deepening the musical skills and understanding of the students. It also gives an opportunity for them to learn various methods of producing music (Department of Education, 2013b).

1. Local Music Genres - (a) Vocal - Songs and Chants; and (b) Instrumental Music in the Community - Indigenous, Folk, Rock, Pop
2. ICT Applications in Music - Jingle Composition, Music Arranging, Music Recording, TV, Radio
3. Vocal and Instrumental Performance Incorporating ICT

Exemplar Research Topics for Local Music Genres

Li, T., Ojihara, M., & Li, Q. (2003, July). A comparative study on content-based music genre classification. In *Proceedings of the 26th annual international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in informaion retrieval* (pp. 282-289).

*Content-based music genre classification is a fundamental component of music information retrieval systems and has been gaining importance and enjoying a growing amount of attention with the emergence of digital music on the Internet. Currently little work has been done on automatic music genre classification, and in addition, the reported classification accuracies are relatively low. This paper proposes a new feature extraction method for music genre classification, DWCHs. DWCHs stands for Daubechies Wavelet Coefficient Histograms. DWCHs capture the local and global information of music signals simultaneously by computing histograms on their Daubechies wavelet coefficients. **Effectiveness of this new feature and of previously studied features are compared using various machine learning classification algorithms, including Support Vector Machines and Linear Discriminant Analysis.** It is demonstrated that the use of DWCHs significantly improves the accuracy of music genre classification.*

Throsby, D. (2002). The music industry in the new millennium: Global and local perspectives. *Global Alliance for Cultural Diversity. Paris: UNESCO–Division of Arts and Cultural Enterprise.*

*This paper **provides a global perspective on the past, present and future state of the world music industry, emphasising both its international dimensions and its local potential.** It begins with an outline of the structure and functioning of music as one of the world's most important cultural industries. It then provides a comprehensive overview of the main trends in the music industry worldwide, with a focus on the regional pattern of production, consumption and trade. Several major issues relating to new trends and challenges in the industry are analysed, including changing patterns of consumption and demand; the changing structure of the industry and trends in market development affecting major record producers and independent labels; the emergence of e-commerce as a factor in the marketplace; and problems of piracy and the enforcement of copyright. The role of music as a force in economic development is briefly reviewed, with particular reference to the Caribbean and Southern Africa, drawing upon recent studies undertaken by UNESCO, UNCTAD, ILO and UNDP. **Finally, the paper makes some concluding observations about the future development of the industry.***

Kruse, H. (2010). Local identity and independent music scenes, online and off. *Popular Music and Society*, 33(5), 625-639.

*Independent music scenes were prominent in the last two decades of the 20th century, but today indie music can be disseminated online, and internet tools allow people in distant locations to engage with each other easily online. With the popularity of the internet, some local spaces devoted to music are becoming less popular and less viable. Yet local spaces continue to provide the infrastructure for music scenes. On the basis of archival research and interviews with scene participants, **this paper argues that the decentralization and globalization of music production and dissemination have not resulted in the disappearance of local identities, local scene histories, or the perception that there are local sounds.***

Exemplar Research Topics for ICT Applications in Music

Aróstegui, J. L. (2010). Risks and promises of ICT for Music Education. *Hellenic journal of music, education and culture*, 1(1).

*This article discusses about the conditions influencing the usage of the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the music classroom. Peter Webster (2002) considers three circumstances allowing or restraining how ICT is employed in music education: (1) technological development; (2) availability and integration; and (3) a constructivist approach being followed for teaching and learning. I will discuss a fourth feature: the similarity between the musical concept supported both by ICT and the school curriculum. I will develop these four circumstances and provide illustrations from a European context. In the ending, I will conclude that **the potentiality of teaching materials that use ICT for music education by can be jeopardized for global and economic interests beyond schools.** ICT is more than being proficient using technologies, but also being an active reader of mass media productions. **Teachers should be aware of both potentials and risks to promote reflective listeners and thinkers rather than reproductive listeners and consumers.***

Chao-Fernandez, R., Román-García, S., & Chao-Fernandez, A. (2017). Analysis of the use of ICT through music interactive games as educational strategy. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 237, 576-580.

*Information and communication technologies have been quickly introduced in all professional and leisure environments. Nonetheless, this process has been slower in educational spheres. ICT contribute and will contribute even further to the renewal of teaching by bringing innovation and creativity. For this reason, we have conducted an investigation in order to ascertain whether through a methodology based on the use of new technologies (ICT) musical knowledge and consequently academic performance of a group of students from 3rd year can be improved. To achieve this goal, two groups of students were selected: one was experimental, who received encouragement (22 learners) and the other group that was controlled (24 students), who worked in Music classroom in a traditional way. The results show that musical learning through the use of ICT improved in 100% of the parameters analysed. For this reason, it is concluded that **it is essential that teachers must seek new teaching methods and strategies to achieve a greater effectiveness of their action as a teacher,** and these techniques should be undoubtedly closely linked with the introduction of ICT in the classroom.*

Portero, G. H., & Bravo, P. C. (2022). The use of ICT in Secondary Music Education and its relationship with teachers' beliefs. *Digital Education Review*, (42), 1-15.

*One of the most notable effects that COVID 19 has engendered in education is the ICT use in teaching at all educational levels. This study provides data on the ICT usage by teachers in the teaching of Music in Secondary Education in Andalusia (Spain). It also explores the relationship between ICT practices and teachers' perceptions of the educational value of ICT for teaching and learning. The empirical results obtained indicate that **Secondary Education Music teachers use ICT in their teaching in a highly heterogeneous manner, with limited use prevailing. A statistically significant relationship is also observed between ICT practices in music teaching and teachers' beliefs regarding the educational value of ICT as a tool for teaching and student learning.***

Exemplar Research Topics for Vocal and Instrumental Performance Incorporating ICT

Sánchez-Jara, J. M. (2014, October). Digital schola: music readers as learning/teaching tools. In *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality* (pp. 547-553).

*The impact of new digital technologies, developed in the last decades, has substantially modified the conception, use and practices, which to the present day, remained immutable for centuries in the world of music and performing arts; from edition or distribution of contents, to production or management of sheet music. In parallel with the emergence and growth of the e-book, it have been developed applications with specific functions and tolos, focused in reading and handling sheet music and musical texts in digital formats. The progressive inclusion, within these applications, of specialized tools for text annotation, study and practice, or music performance, and the present days acknowledgement of them as great educational value resources, has been resolved with the birth of a new category of applications specifically developed for music teaching and learning related purposes. This work aims to **describe the great potential of these new emerging tools, largely in response to a progressive generalization of music as a globalized social practice.** It also describes the various possibilities of use and application in relation to the context, discipline or matter on which they are involved, as well as the different available resources for each particular educational need.*

Bravo, P., González, I., & Bravo, J. (2023). ICT complement for supporting flute study at home. *International Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning*, 15(1), 40-57.

*Many countries propose flute studies in primary school. Usually, students have only one class per week, which makes it inconvenient for teachers to pay attention to students individually. Another problem is that, after lessons, students have to practice alone at home. Thus, the responsibility for progress lies almost entirely with the learner. **This paper proposes a digital tool as a complement to alleviate both problems. The app provides a listening tool, music scores view, records learner performances and offers feedback about students' mistakes during their performances. Finally, the student evolution is sent to the teacher in an adequate manner, to achieve more effective teaching in each class.***

C. Production in the Performing Arts

This course is a showcase of performing arts skills enhanced and developed through a program of apprenticeship (Department of Education, 2013c).

1. Production Organizations and Responsibilities - Musical Director
2. Production Conceptualization and Collaboration with Different Arts - *Creates music appropriate to the production concept.*
3. Production Mounting and Staging - *Rehearses musical numbers with singers, dancers and accompaniment.*
4. Execution of the Production and Post Production - *Showcases creative collaboration in the performing arts exemplified in the pre-production processes, actual performance, and post-performance.*

Exemplar Research Topics for Music Production

Rodgers, T. (2003). On the process and aesthetics of sampling in electronic music production. *Organised Sound*, 8(3), 313-320.

*Most scholars writing on the use of samplers express anxiety over the dissolution of boundaries between human-generated and automated musical expression, and focus on the copyright infringement issues surrounding sampling practices without adequately exploring samplers' musical and political goals. Drawing on musical examples from various underground electronic music genres and on interviews with electronic musicians, this essay addresses such questions as: What is a sampler, and how does the sampling process resonate with or diverge from other traditions of instrument-playing? How do electronic musicians use the 'automated' mechanisms of digital instruments to achieve nuanced musical expression and cultural commentary? What are some political implications of presenting sampled and processed sounds in a reconfigured compositional environment? By exploring these issues, I hope **to counter the over-simplified, uninformed critical claims that sampling is a process of 'theft' and 'automation', and instead offer insight into the myriad and complex musical and political dimensions of sampling in electronic music production.***

Hiller, R. S., & Walter, J. M. (2017). The rise of streaming music and implications for music production. *Review of Network Economics*, 16(4), 351-385.

*In this paper, we model the potential for streaming music, a non-durable product, to upend and displace durable music sales. As the popularity of streaming music increases producers will adjust their production to focus on the non-durable channel. We **identify conditions under which the changes in music delivery will encourage musicians to release fewer songs, but at a higher quality, leading to market deepening and increased engagement. This change will complete the unbundling process in music production making the traditional bundled album of little importance.** This tendency toward unbundling for individual musicians depends on a robust bundle from a delivery platform to provide value for consumer subscriptions. Beyond a model of consumer utility and producer profit, we analyze the most played songs of the large streaming music platform, Spotify, and compare those results to traditional album sales using Nielsen data.*

III. ACADEMIC AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH TOPICS IN MUSIC

Exemplar Research Topics for Measurement and Evaluation of Musical Learning

Tabuena, A. C. (2019). Effectiveness of classroom assessment techniques in improving performance of students in music and piano. *Global Researchers Journal*, 6(1), 68-78.

The primary objective of this study is to determine the effectiveness of classroom assessment techniques in improving the performance of students in Music. This study used an experimental design (paired t-test) to determine the effectiveness of classroom assessment techniques in teaching Music by using purposive sampling of thirty Grade 10 students from the eight sections of Espiritu Santo Parochial School for the school year 2018-2019. The results of pre-evaluation and post-evaluation were compared to determine the effect of classroom assessment techniques on the performance of the students in Music. The results revealed that the students had a low performance in the pre-evaluation and there was an increase in the students' performance in the post-evaluation after its implementation with a mean score of 20.77 and a standard deviation of 3.32. The value of t is 6.680 which is significant at $p < .01$. The result showed that there is a significant difference in the performance of students in music learning in the implementation of classroom assessment techniques. The obtained value of normalized gain (gain of average) was 0.262 inferred to a moderate gain in scores of the students in music learning. The following are the classroom assessment techniques developed and implemented by the researcher (in a large class of 35 to 40 students per class): (1) **Music Concept Memory Exercise**, (2) **Instrumental and Vocal Schematic Processing**, (3) **Five-Letter Name Pitch Memory Test**, and (4) **Three-Chord Familiarization Assessment**.

Tabuena, A. C. (2020). A literature review on the construction of a teacher-made assessment tool in music listening response competency for junior high school K to 12 music curriculum. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*, 8(4), 157-163.

This study reports findings from a literature review study that aimed to describe the principles and processes of constructing a teacher-made assessment tool for Music listening response as one of the needed concepts and skills of Music teachers to address and assess the learning competencies in the junior high school K to 12 Music curriculum for music listening learning competency. Based on the literature review, the researcher identified six themes that are further discussed in this paper: the philosophy and objectives of Music education, the development of Music tests and assessment tools, objective type of tests for listening, forms of Music listening response, assessment tool and test construction, and initiatives and methods on the assessment of Music listening responses. The quality of test construction depends largely on the part of the classroom teacher. The problems of measuring and evaluating students' achievements are not always solved by using standardized tests. The different techniques in constructing teacher-made assessment tools may be a guide to fulfill satisfactorily the measurement that a teacher needs. The objectives, processes, forms, steps, initiatives, and methods in constructing teacher-made tests serve as a guide by the classroom teacher to construct tests scientifically.

Tabuena, A. C. (2020). Development and validation of a Philippine music achievement test in addressing the K to 12 music curriculum learning competencies. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 9(4), 16-25.

The study aimed to develop and validate an achievement test in Philippine Music for Grade 7 junior high school students that can measure the learning competencies in the K to 12 Music Curriculum. The researcher, during the inter-judge consistency process, aligned the learning competencies of Music, the result of which became the basis in preparing the first draft of the test. Based on the test, a set of 115 questions with four options was formulated. The draft of the instrument was submitted to a panel of music experts for content and face validation. Also, the test underwent two tryouts. After the item analysis and the final test administration, a total of 80 items were included in the final form of the test. To ensure reliability, the achievement test underwent the process of the split-half reliability method, the use of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and the correction of the Spearman-Brown Formula applied to the coefficient. The results of the test were reliable at 0.82. Similarly, the data gathered through predictive validity determined by correlating the scores with the subjects' final grades in the Philippine Music Achievement Test (PMAT). **The researcher concluded that the achievement test is valid and reliable for it covers the areas of Music, and the items were responsive to the K to 12 Music learning competencies.**

Exemplar Research Topics for Philosophy and Foundation of Music Education

Tabuena, A. C. (2020). Eclecticism philosophical viewpoint of education: A teaching music philosophy. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 1(7), 67-69.

This analytical essay paper presented the idea of synthesizing the best of several different styles or systems as called eclecticism. Further, it described the eclecticism philosophical viewpoint of education as a teaching music philosophy. The philosophical study of music has many connections with philosophical questions in metaphysics and aesthetics. In this connection, there are three basic philosophical viewpoints in dealing systematically and deeply with the fundamental intellectual issues of life and education; these are not, of course, all-inclusive, such as rationalism, empiricism, and pragmatism. Philosophical viewpoints are examined in relation to four aspects of teaching: curriculum and content, methods of instruction, evaluation, and the roles of teachers and students, to find out the practical effects of these viewpoints on what happens in music classes at a glance. In conclusion, there are different methods and techniques in the teaching of music but there is no definite approach that can be considered the best. There is no standard best procedure for teaching music. Any method, even your own invention, so long as the desired mental effect is produced, is acceptable because, in the teaching of music, reading notes can be syllables, numbers, and letters. **The reason for considering philosophical matters or viewpoints is, teachers can do a much better job of understanding fundamental issues and applying them in their teaching, the benefit of the thinking of some of the great philosophical minds - therefore the philosophical viewpoints have devoted their considerable abilities to dealing systematically and deeply with the fundamental intellectual issues of life and education.**

Tabuena, A. C. (2020). Nature Versus Nurture: A Revisited Explanatory Synthesis on the Development of Musical Abilities. *Universe International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 1(6), 125-132.

This article iterates and synthesizes findings from literature reviews that intended to describe and present the development of musical abilities. In this matter, the ability of music could be both influenced by society and/or by blood, in terms of genes; both science and experience contribute to this development. This study employed a descriptive method to gather information about present existing conditions through a library method and literature review. The data were analyzed using explanatory synthesis. Based on the literature review, the researcher identified two comparative views on the development of musical abilities: nature and nurture. The researcher used four criteria in synthesizing reviews such as cognitive development, intelligence, the relationship between nature and nurture, and musicality is nature, musical ability is nurtured. In conclusion, when it comes to musical ability, nature works in tandem with nurture; musical talent takes nature and nurture. The result of the perception in the origins and appearance of both the intelligence and action dwells in the discernment of how hereditary and social factors are involved in the active and interactional processes that specify and direct its development. The source and power of music could be some determined by association and/or by ancestry, in terms of genes; both scientific discipline and natural event impart to the development of musical abilities.

Exemplar Research Topics for Vocal and Instrumental Music

Tabuena, A. C. (2020). Functional approach as a beginning method for teaching and learning piano accompaniment in music. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 5(1), 51-54.

Piano playing is an integral skill in music education in which students require mastery of the fundamental concepts and principles in terms of piano instruction, as well as in teaching-learning processes. In the part of teaching, which is the piano pedagogy, facilitating learning in playing the piano serves as a ground to develop individuals on a particular skill in each grade level in accordance with the learning competencies enumerated in the Music Curriculum Guide by the Department of Education. This article aimed to describe the context of the functional approach of piano accompaniment to make an easy way of learning the piano accompaniment in the most convenient and fastest time, as well as to accompany certain music or composition in minimal learning time. The practical way of learning piano skills is the observation and use of musical elements through their functions. In this approach, there are four identified components in learning and playing the piano accompaniment: musical elements and functions, musical patterns, musical piano accompaniment styles, and musical piano composition. By this process of learning, gradually, the manner of playing, the style, the elements, and other components of piano accompaniment will be combined to modify and to discover the aesthetic value and characteristics of music composition as well as the wisdom of the music itself.

Tabuena, A. C. (2023, January 13). *Conceptualizing the capstone project through possible research topics, approaches, and methods in music for senior high school students* [Panel Discussion]. University of the Philippines Rural High School, Laguna, Philippines.

Tabuena, A. C. (2020). Chord-interval, direct-familiarization, musical instrument digital interface, circle of fifths, and functions as basic piano accompaniment transposition techniques. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 66(1), 1-11.

This research article aimed to examine and describe different research-based practical and transmedia transposition techniques as basic transposition methods for piano accompaniment. The need for transposition in music, particularly in piano accompaniment, whether in a single line melody, a scale, or an entire composition, is to provide the constituents in the music industry like musicians, pianists, singers, composers, and arrangers with ease and comfortable playing or singing performance using both traditional and/or technological (transmedia) transposition techniques. The most practical way of reading a music sheet is the combination of a lead sheet which composed of the melody and its respective chord/s for each measure or within the measures. Sometimes, song compositions such as folk songs and other traditional songs are just written in a single staff with its defined lyrics. The concern in this matter is the chord that would be used in accompanying the song. In making an accompaniment for this type of music, we could use the three basic types of harmonic progressions in a downward or upward manner by seconds, thirds, and fourths. After learning the basics of chord progressions, the five identified research-based techniques might be used for the process of transposition by church clavinovist and piano enthusiast namely Chord and Interval Transposition Technique, Familiarization and Direct Transposition Technique, Musical Instrument Digital Interface Transposition Technique, Circle of Fifths Transposition Technique, and Functions Transposition Technique.

Tabuena, A. C. (2021). Music of Southeast Asia: Musical ensembles. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(3), 7-11.

This article aimed to characterize the different musical instruments of Southeast Asian countries and distinguish characteristics to its music, culture, and tradition. In addition, the students should be able to explain how the music of a Southeast Asian country relates to its geography and culture, analyze musical elements of selected songs and instrumental pieces heard and performed, explore ways of producing sounds on a variety of sources that would simulate instruments being studied and evaluate music and music performances applying knowledge of musical elements and style.

Exemplar Research Topics for Approaches and Methods of Teaching Music

Tabuena, A. C. (2021). Carabo-Cone, Dalcroze, Kodály, and Orff Schulwerk methods: An explanatory synthesis of teaching strategies in music education. *International Journal of Asian Education*, 2(1), 9-16.

This study emphasizes findings from literature reviews that aimed to describe and present the current teaching strategies in Music education. These teaching strategies are one of the needed primary skills of Music teachers to address the learning challenges, competencies, and diverseness of the existing curriculum, help them to explore the needs of the students, and give them a framework of what could be the best and appropriate strategy in delivering a lesson. This study employed a descriptive method to gather information about present conditions through a library method and literature review. The data were analyzed using explanatory synthesis. Based on the literature review, the researcher identified four well-known teaching strategies in Music education: the Carabo-Cone Method, Dalcroze Method, Kodaly Method, and Orff Schulwerk Approach. The researcher used four criteria in synthesizing reviews such as the proponent, foundation, philosophy, and methodology. Conclusion of the results and discussions, the four teaching strategies also varied in four indicators, yet similarly focused on using the senses for holistic growth and development and providing all students with the opportunity to be successful. The quality of education depends mostly on the part of the teacher. The different Music teaching strategies serve as a guide to fulfilling the purpose satisfactorily that a teacher and a student needs. It is recommended to analyze its implications towards different modes of learning as global education facing numerous challenges in terms of economic crisis, pandemic, and educational incapability and inequalities that could affect the educational system.

Tabuena, A. C. (2021). South and West Asian Music: A Brief Teaching Discussion of the Music of India and Israel. *Indiana Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(1), 27-31.

This article (short communication) was initiated to aid both teachers and students in the teaching-learning process in music, specifically in South and West Asian music in the Philippine K-12 junior high school music curriculum. This brief teaching discussion is intended for Grade 8 junior high school students, particularly in the third grade period under the Asian music subject. This brief teaching discussion will just focus on one country per region in Asia: India for South Asia, and Israel for West Asia. That is, the brief method is applicable for both distance (online, modular, blended, flexible) and traditional modes of learning. The discussion will focus on the cultural backgrounds, characteristics, and vocal and instrumental music of the two countries, which are aligned in the content and performance standards, as well as learning competencies, of the aforementioned curriculum. In this initiative in music education, teachers and students characterized the different musical instruments of South and West Asian countries and distinguished characteristics of their music, culture, and tradition.

Exemplar Research Topics for Music in Development

Tabuena, A. C. (2022). The Secrets of Hope and Faith: Resilience in Philippine Music as the Country's Unique Culture. *Indiana Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 62-67.

This lecture and review article aims to share the secrets of hope and faith, the resilience of Philippine music and music education as the country's unique culture in celebration of National Arts Month 2022, its artistic excellence and pay tribute to the uniqueness and diversity of Filipino heritage and culture. In line with the theme, Sining ng Pag-asa, it seeks to recognize the arts as a source and expression of hope, as demonstrated by the creative ways in which we respond to the effects of the pandemic, natural disasters, and other social realities, as well as the arts' role in improving our community life as Filipinos. This article answers three significant questions. How does Philippine music, or music in general, give hope amidst the pandemic? What is the most evident characteristic of Philippine music that portrays hope? What could be the factors that Filipinos are encountering in their daily lives that cause them to have these kinds of characteristics in their music? Clearly, our musical heritage reveals a lot about who we are. Learning about Filipino music cultures is the first step to gaining a deeper understanding of the Filipino people. The pandemic taught us a lot of things. Whatever the case may be, we have always recovered and survived. It has taught us to rethink the value of life, health, and even leaders. Some may believe there is no hope. But, as we fight COVID-19, let us not forget our two most powerful weapons—faith and music.

Buenaflor, M. P., Tabuena, A. C., Morales, G. S., & Perez, M. L. A. C. (2022). Associated Determinants and Music Genres in A Few Fitness Facilities. *Journal of Humanities, Music and Dance*, 2(6), 16-24.

Exercisers often listen to music as they work out, which may boost their levels of motivation and good affect respectively. It is possible to play it through a sound system while you are working out. The purpose of the research was to look at the different types of music that are played in various fitness centers and analyze the factors that are connected with certain types of music. It used an exploratory approach to the study design. A community in which there are a total of four fitness centers was chosen for this experiment. Research was conducted on each and every teacher working at those centers. It was determined to adopt a key informant interview (KII) guide. In order to identify the differences that were statistically significant, a one-way ANOVA and Tukey post hoc tests were carried out. According to the results of the research, classical music was listened to the most, with a mean of 5.177. 06 times, whilst twist was listened to the least, with a mean of 0.750. 82 times. Only listening to classical music was substantially ($p < 0.05$) different between fitness centers 1 and 2, but in general, there were no significant changes among the various fitness centers. The kind of exercise, the client's age, and their religious affiliation were revealed to be key predictors. Other factors that were taken into consideration were the customers' health, as well as their personal interests, objectives, goals, and role models, as well as the clients' requests, the time of day, and the gender of the instructor.

Tabuena, A. C., Morales, G. S., & Perez, M. L. A. C. (2022). The value of music education in the development of internationally competent students. *Journal of Humanities, Music and Dance*, 2(2), 13-18.

*The music that is played at school and the music that is played at home vary significantly for the majority of teenagers, despite the fact that music is highly important to them and plays a large part in their life. This is true despite the fact that most teenagers place a high value on music. Teenagers have a broad range of musical preferences, according to research, and these disparities may be attributed to a number of personal and societal factors. **The researcher makes a case for incorporating non-Western musical idioms into the music curriculum and addresses the issue of insufficient music education in Croatian elementary schools. The author specifically supports the inclusion of popular music and music from other cultures in the curriculum.** The author also argues in favor of broadening the scope of music lessons by including non-Western musical traditions into the curriculum. **Students who participate in music education will acquire the skills necessary to perform successfully in a variety of situations throughout the world.***

IV. OTHER RESEARCH TOPICS FOR THE ARTS

Exemplar Research Topics for the Arts

Tabuena, A. C., & Domingo, C. P. (2021). Analyzing Contemporary Philippine Art Forms and Critiquing Available Local Materials and Appropriate Techniques Used in Creating Art. *International Journal of Applied Arts Studies*, 6(1), 83-100.

*The way art is understood has been formalized. **The primary objective of this paper is to acquaint the students with one of the methods in analyzing contemporary Philippine art forms and critiquing available local materials and appropriate techniques used in creating art.** As part of the subject course in Contemporary Philippine Arts from the Regions, one of the core subjects in the Senior High School curriculum in the Philippines under the K-12 curriculum, one of the methods implemented in critiquing contemporary Philippine artworks is **the Analysis-Interpretation-Discernment Method or the AID Method.** This method will be carried out together with the description applied to contemporary art and the knowledge in the elements, principles, and contexts of arts. Criticism can be construed positively. Several critics discuss their reactions to various forms of art and weigh in on the works' merits. One may not always agree with their assessments, as the criteria or standards of evaluation may differ significantly from those of the professional critic. In this circumstance, visiting contemporary art exhibitions and conversing with living artists is critical for developing a knowledge and appreciation for the Philippine arts and culture. **The purpose of art criticism gives a significant role in the process of inquiry in relation to contemporary arts, that is, to distinguish the different contexts of art to a familiar art form as well as to appraise the culture of the Philippine arts with awareness and appreciation.***

Tabuena, A. C., Bravo, C. D. S., Dimalanta, F. D. R., Jusay, K. A. P., & Vitug, M. Y. (2022). **Inclination State on the Philippine Culture and Arts Using the Appraisal Theory: Factors of Progress and Deterioration.** *Participatory Educational Research*, 9(1), 388-403.

This study aimed to examine the inclination state among selected Filipinos using the Appraisal Theory in evaluating the appreciation level as an advocacy perspective towards the Philippine culture and arts. This study employed a transformative mixed method research design, both quantitative and qualitative views were considered through a survey questionnaire, an interview, and an assessment process conducted at Espiritu Santo Parochial School of Manila, Inc. and the National Commission for Culture and the Arts, Philippines. They were selected through convenience-quota and purposive sampling based on the subjects' basic knowledge and appreciation of Philippine culture and heritage. The data were analyzed using frequency distribution and content analysis. Hake factor analysis was also used to measure the appraisal level in terms of art awareness and appreciation. The results revealed that the respondents grasped a high appraisal of the Philippine culture and arts. This implied progress factors in terms of art as a form of communication, museums as the priority tool for preservation and promotion, and the country's identity and cultural history as to reframe art appreciation. On the contrary, they adapted more to the culture and arts of other countries than to cultural roots due to factors that cause it to deteriorate such as foreign cultures and modern technologies adaptation, lack of knowledge and participation, and the primordialism of ethnocentrism. The researchers assessed that the theory exposed understanding emotions as it is evident that the respondents can reframe others with their beliefs and values towards Philippine culture and arts.

Tabuena, A. C. (2022). **Creative Expression on How Do Artists Communicate Their Message: An Arts in Development Article Critique.** *Asian Journal of Arts and Culture*, 22(2), 257372.

This article critique aims to determine and evaluate the strengths and shortcomings of the article titled "Creative Expression—How do Artists communicate their message?" by Evan Tublitz in 2014, reviewed and critiqued in order to evaluate and analyze the role of art and artists in development and to draw new perspectives on life, as art is primarily a means of communication. Language-bound ideas are often conveyed through painting, sculpture, and music, and they do so to reveal new perspectives, just like other artists. Seeing and understanding artwork is necessary to express oneself and understand the world. This attitude comes through in the art. The artistic framing and communication of ideas captivated the author to consider the whole piece or section to form an intellectual idea—an artist shapes and glazes clay to express ideas; artists, like musicians, begin with an idea. During this event, we all maximized our contributions to the bodies of knowledge, liberty, and freedom. In addition, there are many ways to express oneself in photography. The artist gives us a new perspective as it shows how intellectual and emotional concepts influence perceptions of the world. Emotions, thoughts, images, and ideas are elicited by humans who want to educate, persuade, move, and broaden their minds. In conclusion, the artist as philosopher's role is to inspire, comprehend, and transform others, and possibly to transfer this knowledge. Art is created to express itself. The audience consumes and interacts with art, where ideas are acquired and communicated.

Tabuena, A. C. (2023, January 13). *Conceptualizing the capstone project through possible research topics, approaches, and methods in music for senior high school students* [Panel Discussion]. University of the Philippines Rural High School, Laguna, Philippines.

Tabuena, A. C. (2021). A synthesis overview of the contemporary art forms and performance practices in the Philippines. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Studies*, 7(1), 103-109.

This research article describes and presents an overview of the contemporary art forms and performance practices from the various regions in the Philippines. Visiting contemporary art exhibitions and talking about living artists is an important aspect of appraising the culture of the Philippine arts with awareness and appreciation. This study used a descriptive method to gather information about existing conditions in which the library method and literature review were utilized in gathering and synthesizing the articles and scientific papers related to contemporary Philippine art. The data were analyzed through synthesis information known as explanatory synthesis through the use of eight criteria in analyzing the reviews such as painting and other visual arts, architecture, sculpture and installation, literature, music, dance, cinema, and theater and performance. Conclusion of the results and discussions, contemporary Philippine art encompasses a wide range of art forms and constantly redefines and dismantles traditional categories of arts. Philippine traditional art has always been an integral part of daily life, as well as the dominant and alternative art forms. Its importance endures not only in its aesthetic representation but also in its functionality and its significance to the society that created it. As the dominant, alternative, and traditional art forms may be used in everyday private circumstances, it is encountered more closely and possesses many senses concurrently.

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Profiles

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